

DAMAGES OF SMOKING

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Abstract: Have smokers thought at least once about the extent to which smoking harms the body? Smoking harms not only the person himself, but also the people around him. Inhaling tobacco smoke damages your health, your immune system, and your respiratory and cardiovascular systems.

Key words: smoking, nicotine, health, problems, cigarettes, smokers, addiction

Harms of smoking

DAMAGE OF CIGARETTE TO THE HUMAN ORGANISM

Even children know that one drop of nicotine can kill a horse. However, this evidence does not make a special impression on smokers: they fool themselves with the statement that it is impossible to smoke so many cigarettes at the same time. However, the harm of tobacco smoke is not related to nicotine itself, it only causes addiction, the destructive effects of smoking are also expressed by other factors. Along with cigarette smoke, the smoker also ingests the following substances:

Margimush. This poison causes heart problems, causes cancer and is very difficult to get out of the body.

Formaldehyde. This toxic chemical compound primarily affects the respiratory system.

Polonium. This element has radioactive properties. 40% of "experienced" smokers regularly ingest polonium particles.

Benzene. This organic substance is the first cause of leukemia and other oncological diseases.

Resin. Tar from cigarette smoke remains in the lungs as a deposit. Over time, it increases more and more, narrows the bronchi, reduces the volume of the lungs and, as a result, worsens the access of oxygen to the body.

These substances are not the only poisons that are part of tobacco smoke. As standard chemical testing of cigarettes confirms, each puff means inhaling a mixture of many toxic substances, including:

Toxic gases and vapors: methanol, ammonia, butane, methane, hydrogen sulfide, carbon monoxide;

Organic compounds: cyanic acid, acetone, phenol, carbazole, indole;

Heavy metals: lead, radium, cadmium, cesium, aluminum, antimony.

None of these components are safe - each of them damages the body in one way or another, weakens the immune system, negatively affects the functioning of the lungs, enters the bloodstream, disrupts the work of the heart, brain and other organs, causes cell mutation comes and causes oncology.

MEDICAL STATISTICS

The consequences of smoking can be very different - tobacco smoke affects almost all internal organs. However, the most common complications of this harmful habit are:

Chronic bronchitis;

Oncological diseases of the respiratory system;

Cardiovascular pathologies (IHF, arterial hypertension, vascular thrombosis, etc.).

Statistics also confirm that 90 percent of patients with lung cancer have a history of smoking. In addition, 75 percent of deaths from bronchitis and emphysema are related to this harmful habit in one way or another. Heart disease in smokers is also 25% more severe and causes more death.

People who have never smoked are 13 times less likely to suffer from angina pectoris, 12 times less likely to suffer from myocardial infarction, and 10 times less likely to suffer from stomach ulcer attacks.

There is no organ that does not suffer from cigarette smoke: the heart of smokers beats an average of 650 beats per hour more than that of non-smokers, and even then they cannot supply the body with enough oxygen. First, the air enters the lungs in a very small volume, and secondly, the carbon dioxide from cigarette smoke combines with hemoglobin and disrupts oxygen exchange in the body. As a result, the brain, liver, kidneys, digestive system and reproductive system are damaged, and the morbidity and mortality rates increase significantly.

DAMAGE OF CIGARETTE SMOKING FOR WOMEN

A woman's body reacts to tobacco more significantly than a man's. In addition to the main diseases, as a result of smoking, women lose their beauty, youth and, most importantly, the opportunity to become a mother.

The rate of infertility in women who smoke regularly is 42 percent. Among those who are not familiar with smoking, this indicator is 4 percent.

When smoking, nails and hair suffer from a lack of oxygen, become dull and brittle, and almost stop growing. Due to tobacco smoke, the teeth are gradually destroyed, and no chewing gum can hide the unpleasant smell from the mouth. Skin looks 10-15 years older than normal.

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